

EARTH SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY TO SOLVE THE PROBLEM OF GRAVIMETRY

E. İsgandarov,

Associate professor,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU),

Baku, Azerbaijan

L. İsgandarova

Senior student,

Department of "Computer engineering" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU),

Baku, Azerbaijan,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10277016>

Abstract

As is known, computer technology and programming are widely used in geophysics when solving the problem of field transformation as well as solving direct and inverse problems. The direct task of gravity exploration is to calculate the gravitational influence of geological bodies, and then compare the theoretical values of gravity with the observed values, which makes it possible to more accurately solve the main problem of gravity exploration – geological problem. In gravity exploration, when solving a direct problem, the concept of a two-dimensional body is often used, in which one dimension, usually along the y axis, is infinite and the other two along the x and z axis are limited. The article describes the algorithm and block-diagram for calculating the vertical and horizontal component of gravity for two-dimensional bodies of arbitrary shape, as well as the results of using the FORCE-FORTRAN program GRAVIT compiled by the authors of the article using the example of a model geological two-dimensional body of arbitrary shape.

Keywords: numerical methods, direct problem, algorithm, gravity survey, two-dimensional body.

Introduction

Computational mathematics and programming play a large role in solving engineering problems and calculations. In this case, the use of numerical methods of calculation and analysis occupies an important place. In the mathematical formulation of problems, two classes can be distinguished, to which many of the problems considered in numerical analysis belong. A direct computational problem in which, given an element belonging to a certain space Y and an operator F that transforms elements of Y into elements of space Z, it is necessary to find the function $Z=F(Y)$, for example, finding the integral of $Y(X)$ is a direct computational problem. Here $F(Y)=\int_0^1 Y(X)dX$. In the case of an inverse computational problem, when given an element Z and an operator F that transforms elements Y into elements Z, it is necessary to find such a Y in order to solve the equation. Many computational problems, direct inverse, can have elements of infinite-dimensional spaces Y and Z as elements Y and Z, for example functions $F(X)$. Such problems are called continuous in contrast to discrete ones, where Y and Z are elements of finite-dimensional spaces. Discrete problems include computational problems of linear algebra, for example, solving a system of linear equations. Analytical and perturbation methods can operate on objects such as functions. Numerical methods, if they are intended to be implemented on a computer, cannot operate with objects that require an infinite set of numbers to describe due to limited computer memory [1,9].

Numerical methods of analysis and computational mathematics and engineering are also widely used in

earth sciences. These include, for example, geology and geophysics, the purpose of which is to study the structure of the earth's crust for the search and exploration of mineral deposits. Among geophysical methods, along with seismic prospecting and electrical prospecting, gravity and magnetic prospecting is also widely used. Gravity exploration studies the distribution of the gravity field on the earth's surface, which makes it possible to identify density inhomogeneities of rocks in the earth's crust. As is known, minerals and minerals differ in their density properties from the host rocks. In gravity prospecting, as in geophysics, this involves solving direct and inverse problems using numerical methods and programming. The direct problem is the problem of modeling geophysical data, which is used for two-dimensional and three-dimensional geological objects [2,7].

The results of research in this area are covered in many works [2-8]. The article analyzes methods, algorithms and programs for solving the direct problem of gravity exploration using a computer, which is important for solving the main inverse geological problem.

Methodology

As is known, in a two-dimensional problem, we consider fields created by bodies of infinite length and constant cross-section, elongated across the profile line x. In this case, the vertical component of gravity acceleration [7] will be:

$$V_z(x, z) = 2G\rho \iint_0^Q \frac{(z-z')d\xi d\zeta}{(\xi-x)^2 + (z-z')^2}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ is the excess density of the geological body; G is the gravitational constant, and integration is

carried out over the entire cross-sectional area of the body Q.

Discretizing the spatial coordinates with sufficiently small increments Δx and Δz , we denote:

$$x_i = i\Delta x; z_k = k\Delta z; \zeta_l = l\Delta \zeta; \xi_j = j\Delta \xi.$$

Then:

$$V_z(i, k) = 2G\rho \sum_i \sum_j \frac{(\zeta_l - z_k)\Delta z \Delta x}{(\xi_j - x_i)^2 + (\zeta_l - z_k)^2} \quad (2)$$

For the horizontal field component:

$$V_x(x, z) = 2G\rho \int_0^Q \frac{(\xi - x)d\xi dz}{(\xi - x)^2 + (\zeta - z)^2}, \quad (3)$$

We get similarly:

$$V_x(i, k) = 2G\rho \sum_l \sum_j \frac{(\xi_j - x_i)\Delta z \Delta x}{(\xi_j - x_i)^2 + (\zeta_l - z_k)^2}, \quad (4)$$

The summation is carried out for all points inside the contour of the section Q. Note that the assumption used about the homogeneity of the body (constant density ρ) is not necessary, but with a variable density the volume of data prepared to solve the problem increases.

A two-dimensional problem is solved for a homogeneous body with density ρ . The field components VX (I) and VZ (I) on the earth's surface $z = 0$ are equal:

$$VX(I) = A \sum_L \sum_J \frac{J-I}{(J-I)^2 + L^2} \quad (5)$$

$$VZ(I) = A \sum_L \sum_J \frac{L}{(J-I)^2 + L^2}, \quad (6)$$

where I is an abscissa of the observation point on the earth's surface; J, L are the square grid nodes in the contour of the anomaly-forming body; I, J, L are integer numbers; $A = 2G \times \rho \times D$, $D = \Delta x = \Delta z$ – grid step (sampling step); G is a gravitational constant.

The main problem is specifying the section of the body within which the summation over L and J is performed. Specifying the section of the body is performed as follows. At each depth L, the abscissas of the left (J1) and right (J2) edges of the body are specified. It is assumed that the body has a sufficiently simple shape for such a description to be unambiguous.

Thus, the section of the body is described by two arrays J1 and J2, which, when calculating the field, are

analyzed within depths from L1 (upper boundary of the body) to L2 (lower boundary of the body).

The required values of the field components VX, VZ are calculated at each point I by searching through depths L from L1 to L2 and horizontal coordinates from J1 (L) to J2 (L).

Main part

At the beginning, based on the algorithm described above, a block diagram of the algorithm for calculating the horizontal and vertical components of gravity from a homogeneous two-dimensional body with some excess density was drawn

up (Fig. 1). Based on this algorithm, the FORTRAN program GRAVIT was compiled using the FORCE FORTRAN compiler, a fragment of which is shown in the figure (Fig. 2). This program was then edited and compiled. To work with this program, a two-dimensional body of arbitrary shape was first prepared using the WORD office program using a grid view (Fig. 3). Then, based on the cross-section of a two-dimensional body, the initial data were prepared in accordance with the GRAVIT program, shown on the printout (Fig. 4). As you can see, the value of the excess density of a two-dimensional body was chosen to be 0.2 g/cm³, which is typical for Mesozoic volcanogenic-sedimentary deposits in Azerbaijan. Based on the results obtained, curves of the vertical and horizontal components Vz and Vx were constructed using the EXEL program. (Fig. 5-6). The summary figure shows a section of a two-dimensional body and the Vz and Vx curves (Fig. 7). As you can see, the Vz curve increases from left to right and reaches its maximum value of 16 mGal just above the center of gravity of an arbitrary body. The Vx curve from left to right changes its sign from negative to positive, reaching a maximum modulo value of 8 mGal.

Fig.1. Block diagram of the GRAVIT algorithm

```

1 | PROGRAM GRAVIT
2 | DIMENSION VX(50),VZ(50),J1(20),J2(20)
3 | OPEN(5,FILE='ISX')
4 | OPEN(6,FILE='REZ')
5 | READ(5,55) H,M,L1,L2,D,RO
6 | 55 FORMAT(4I2,2F3.1)
7 | WRITE(6,*) ' H,M,L1,L2,D,RO '
8 | WRITE(6,58)H,M,L1,L2,D,RO
9 | 58 FORMAT(5X,4I5,2F10.1)
10 | READ(5,56) (J1(I),I=1,M)
11 | READ(5,56) (J2(I),I=1,M)
12 | 56 FORMAT(8I2)
13 | WRITE(6,*) ' J1 AND J2 '
14 | WRITE(6,57) (J1(I),I=1,M)
15 | WRITE(6,57) (J2(I),I=1,M)
16 | 57 FORMAT(5X,8I2)
17 | A=2*RO*D*.67
18 | WRITE(6,59) A
19 | 59 FORMAT(5X,'A=',F6.2)
20 | DO 10 I=1,N
21 | VX(I)=0.
22 | VZ(I)=0.
23 | K=0
24 | DO 10 L=L1,L2
25 | K=K+1
26 | J1L=J1(K)
27 | J2L=J2(K)
28 | DO 10 J=J1L,J2L
29 | Q=(J-I)**2+L**2
30 | VX(I)=VX(I)+A*(J-I)/Q

```

Fig.2. Fragment of the GRAVIT FORCE-FORTRAN program

Fig.3. Specifying a section of a two-dimensional body

```

N.M.L1.L2.D.R.O
14 5 1 5 1.0 0.2
J1 AND J2
6 6 6 5 6
8 8 8 9 9
A= 2.67
VX AND VZ
6.1 6.8 7.4 7.9 8.0 5.4 0.2 -5.1 -7.7 -7.8
-7.3 -6.7 -6.2 -5.6
3.1 4.0 5.4 7.3 10.4 14.7 16.3 14.8 10.6 7.6
5.6 4.2 3.3 2.6
    
```

Fig.4. Printed source data and calculation results

Fig.5. Vz curve from an arbitrary two-dimensional body

Fig.6. Vx curve from an arbitrary two-dimensional body

Fig.7. Results of the GRAVIT program

Findings

1. The issue of using numerical methods of mathematics and programming to solve the direct problem of gravity exploration in a two-dimensional version is analyzed.

2. An algorithm and an appropriate block diagram for solving the direct problem of gravity exploration have been compiled.

3. A program for solving the direct problem of gravity exploration was compiled on a computer in the FORCE-FORTRAN algorithmic language, and the GRAVIT program was edited and debugged.

4. Initial data for a model of a two-dimensional geological body of arbitrary shape have been prepared and the formalization of the problem has been completed.

5. The vertical and horizontal components of gravity were calculated for a two-dimensional body using the GRAVIT program on a computer.

6. Based on the calculation results using the EXCEL program, curves of the vertical and horizontal

components of gravity were constructed and the behavior of these curves for this two-dimensional model was analyzed.

7. The program compiled by FORCE-FORTRAN can be used to solve the problem of modeling in gravity exploration for two-dimensional bodies of arbitrary shape at the stage of geological data interpretation.

References:

1. Boglaev Yu. P. Computational mathematics and programming: Textbook manual for university students. – M.: Higher. school, 1990. – 544 p. (in Russian).
2. Dmitrieva V. I. Computational mathematics and technology in exploration geophysics: Textbook manual for university students. – M.: Nedra, 1990. – 498 p. (in Russian).
3. Isgandarov E.H. Digital modeling of the gravitational field of the Muradkhanly rise. Australian Journal of Education and Science. Australia. Sidney university. 2018 il, p.9. (in Russian).

4. Isgandarov E.H. Transformation of gravemagnetic anomalies. Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan-French University (UFAZ), PARCECO Unistra Scientific Conference, Baku, Azerbaijan, November 30 - December 1, 2021.

5. İsgandarov E.H., Seyidov V.M.. Digital modeling of analytical continuation of gravitational field. German International Journal of Modern Science EARTH SCIENCES, № 29, 2022, pp.11-14. ISSN 2701-8377.

6. Isgandarov E.H. Digital estimation of the gravitational effect of the crystalline basement of the Yevlakh-Agjabadi Basin (Middle-Kur Depression).

Azerbaijan National Academy of sciences. ANAS TRANSACTIONS EARTH SCIENCES, Geology and Geophysics institute, ISSN 2218-8754 , 2023 , № 1. (Elsevier-Scobus),pp. 17-24.

7. Rapoport M. B. Computing technology in field geophysics. M.: Nedra, 1984, p.264 p (in Russian)

8. İsgandarov E., Jabizadeh L. Digital modeling of gravity anomalies, Polish journal of science, № 61 (2023), pp.25-32, ISSN 3353-2389, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7835027.

9. http://mathprofi.ru/ploshad_v_poljarnyh_koordinatah.html.